

An effective conventional powder metallurgy route using elemental powders for the development of Cu-Al-Ni shape memory alloys

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During recent years, Cu-based Shape Memory Alloys (SMAs) are in great demand due to their potential use as sensors, actuators and damping devices. In particular, Cu-Al-Ni alloys possess high thermal stability at elevated temperatures, i.e., above 373 K, making them suitable for high temperature. The preparation of these alloys through casting route results in a coarse-grained structure, which further coarsened during subsequent heat treatment. As a result, the mechanical properties especially ductility of the alloy becomes relatively poor due to brittleness and limit their applications. It has been suggested that the powder metallurgy processing may be a better alternative to enhance the ductility of the SMAs as this processing route may lead to more stable fine grained structure. Initially, the mechanical alloying of the elemental powders in order to make a mechanically alloyed powder having the desired composition. One of the most important features of the Cu-Al-Ni SMAs produced by the powder metallurgy route is that the products have finer grains as compared to those produced by the liquid metallurgy route. Further, requirement of long milling time & milling in inert atmosphere for mechanically alloyed powder are very expensive and energy inefficient. Moreover, mechanical alloying may cause introduction of impurities and unwanted secondary phases in the matrix. Therefore, it was felt necessary to develop a simple powder metallurgy process (mixing, compaction and sintering/hot pressing) which can provide Cu-based shape memory material with homogeneous and controlled composition possessing improved properties. Preparation of the mixture of elemental powders in required composition followed by thorough mixing in dry condition followed by controlled heating cycle with pressure assistance. The sintered samples were further solutionized followed by quenching. Further the study was performed to observe the effect of aluminum concentration on the microstructure and phase evolution of the Cu based SMA. The FE-SEM and XRD analysis indicate that complete formation of martensite occurred in all the cases. However, increasing aluminum concentration resulted in the formation of higher amount of γ' martensite.

Keywords: Powder metallurgy, Shape memory alloy, Cu-Al-Ni, martensite